

Trident™ Thermal Conductivity Application Highlight: Monitoring Resin Stability and Sedimentation with MTPS

The following Application Highlight summarizes the use of C-Therm's MTPS method in monitoring the stability of a filled resin system.

Thermally conductive adhesives are a key component for thermal management of many advanced electronic systems. These materials help dissipate heat in ensuring an optimal operating temperature is maintained. As an example, this is critical to battery pack performance in electric vehicles where thermal runaway mitigation and performance require optimal thermal management. Unaltered, these resin adhesive materials typically have low thermal conductivity ($< 0.3\text{W/mK}$). To obtain higher thermal conductivity materials ($>1\text{ W/mK}$), conductive fillers such as alumina, boron nitride etc., can be introduced into the base resin to increase thermal dissipation output by providing improved paths of heat transfer (see Fig. 1). This has been the focus on many groups working on formulation development of these composite materials (*Some example publications can be found at the end of this document*). This, however, possesses its own unique set of issues, especially when scaling to large quantity applications.

Figure 1. Left) Disorganized polymer chains resulting in phonon scattering (poor thermal conduction). Right) Filled system with improved heat transfer paths (increased thermal conduction).

Small, portable electronics may only require milligram to gram quantities of these materials to achieve the desired performance. For large scale applications such as EV battery packs, the volume of material required increases significantly. As such, the feedstock containers used in these larger applications may hold upwards of 200 liters of resin (see Fig. 2). While there are many advanced pieces of equipment to aid in the proper mixing, dispensing, and curing of these materials, if there are inherent issues with the feedstock material itself, the end product can suffer. One consideration revolves around filler sedimentation of the material.

Figure 2. Example of scale differences for material and filler from different dispensing feedstock vessels. Left) Exhibiting ideal dispersion of filler. Right) Exhibiting noticeable sedimentation.

Sedimentation is a process in which the filler material will settle out of suspension towards the bottom of the containment vessel (see Fig. 3). This differs from particle agglomeration, which describes the formation of particle groupings in a suspension leading to the destabilization of a colloidal system. There are many factors that can influence sedimentation including the resin viscosity, storage conditions, filler density, stabilizing agents, etc. Even well-formulated stable products can start to separate if used past their shelf life or if stored improperly. It is therefore useful to have a means of monitoring the extent to which sedimentation occurs on a formulation in a lab formulation environment, but also to consider in-line measurement for traceability on the product consistency at the point of dispensing in manufacturing. The benefit of avoiding a QA/QC failure downstream or future product recall is substantial given the costs to rework/scrap, product recall, damage to reputation and legal liability.

Figure 3. Left) Depiction of a "good" suspension. Right) Example of sediment formation.

The following is an example highlighting C-Therm's MTPS in the measurement of a filled system exhibiting sedimentation. A column was filled with one part of a 2k resin system containing an alumina filler at different wt.% loadings. The column was placed overtop the MTPS sensor and measurements were taken as a function of time. Over time there is a visible gradient formed within the column as the sedimentation process developed (Fig. 4).

Figure 4. Visualization of alumina powder settling (overnight trials).

The data below shows thermal conductivity steadily increasing over the measurement duration correlating to the settling of the filler towards the bottom on the column. The extent and speed to which the increase occurred can be related to the wt.% of filler studied. It should be noted that no thixotropic agent or surfactants were added to the system to reduce the sedimentation/agglomeration process in this data set.

Figure 5. Thermal conductivity as a function of time quantifying the sedimentation process.

C-Therm's Trident platform employing the MTPS sensor is ideal for benchtop R&D applications, however the same sensor technology has a history of also being incorporated for in-line applications and process monitoring (see Fig. 6).

Figure 6. C-Therm's MTPS (ESP) sensor used for in-line process monitoring of a wide variety of fluids

To learn more about the application of C-Therm's patented thermal sensors for in-line monitoring contact us below.

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